

Algorithmic Generation of Mass Energy Values for Bosons and Leptons

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I. ABSTRACT

We present a novel algorithm, based on an entangled three-cube quantum lattice system, with the purpose of calculating rest-mass energy values for the elementary particles via the Higgs Vacuum Expectation Value (VEV) and the Planck Mass energy value.

The results from algorithmically generated mass-values for bosons and leptons are presented. All together 18 values, covering an energy range of almost 7 decades. The average difference from the PDG-values we used as reference was below 2% RMS.

The algorithmic approach is subsequently extended to include neutrino mass-values, based on data concerning mass sums and squared mass splitting from the Particle Data Group (PDG). The calculated neutrino mass sum differs from values, calculated via the NuFIT- mass splitting by less than one percent. The results are based on the assumption of Normal Hierarchy.

By comparing mass-values generated by the algorithm via Higgs VEV and the Planck Mass, we have calculated two sets of mass-values within two energy ranges, currently being explored for bosons not included in the standard model.

The first such energy range lies between 40- and 180 μeV . This range is assumed to include the mass for the axion boson, generally connected to the Strong CP-problem. Two pairs of almost identical values were generated, both within the range of interest.

The second energy range, between 90-and 260 GeV is reported to be of interest for probing Higgs boson doublet models at LHC. We found five energy value pairs of which two were closely related to the value of the Higgs boson.

The comparison method via Higgs VEV and Planck has generated mass-values for the bosons of the Standard model, typically around two percent of the PDG-listed values. By extrapolation of the results, we have calculated mass-values within the ranges mentioned above, both of which are supposed to be related to dark matter.

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